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Could Negative Multiparametric MRI of the Prostate Obviate the Need for Biopsy? A Prospective Feasibility Pilot Study

Monday, Nov. 26 12:15PM - 12:45PM Room: GU/UR Community, Learning Center Station #1

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PURPOSE

To investigate the feasibility of follow up in men with elevated prostate-specific antigen (PSA) level, negative digital rectal exam (DRE) and negative multiparametric MRI (mpMRI).

METHOD AND MATERIALS

Over the period of 13 years, 36 men (age range at the time of the inclusion 45-71 years (mean 64)) with PSA level elevation, negative DRE and negative mpMRI were included in the study. All men were followed up clinically, including PSA and DRE, and with mpMRI. mpMRI examinations included thin slice (3mm) T2 weighted images in three planes, diffusion-weighted images, dynamic postcontrast images in all men and MR spectroscopy in the most.

RESULTS

Mean follow up was 6.4 years, (range from 16 months to 13 years), mean PSA level during the study was 7.3ng/L (range 1.72-11.29ng/L), mean initial PSA was 8.7ng/L (range 4.3-13.2ng/L). All participants were followed clinically, none of them underwent a single biopsy. After initial negative mpMRI first follow up mpMRI was in 6 months, then one year, and further according to the clinical finding (3-5 follow up mpMRI in total per men). None of the men were diagnosed with prostate cancer; three men died due to cardiovascular disease, two developed other malignancies (one colorectal, other lung cancer).

CONCLUSION

In men with increased PSA, negative mpMRI of the prostate can obviate the need for biopsy.

CLINICAL RELEVANCE/APPLICATION

It could be feasible to follow up men with clinically suspected prostate cancer and negative mpMRI safely.